

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

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A twelve-year experience in treatment of children with radiotherapy at The Institute of Oncology and Radiology of Serbia

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Introduction: Radiotherapy has an important role in the treatment of children with cancer. The aim of this study was to provide analysis of children treated with radiotherapy in a national referral institution in Serbia in a twelve-year period.

Material and Methods: A retrospective medical chart review on a series of 767 children treated with radiotherapy between 2007 and 2018 was performed.

Results: The most common tumors were brain tumors, leukemias and bone sarcomas. Most children received radiotherapy in adjuvant setting. One hundred and fifteen patients required anesthesia or sedation during simulation and treatment sessions. The five-year and ten-year overall survival rates were 65.7% and 62.1%, respectively. Tumor type and intent of radiotherapy had significant impact on survival. Patients with retinoblastoma, lymphomas and nephroblastoma had the best survival rates, while the worst survival rate was obtained in group of patients with bone sarcomas. Patients treated with palliative and definitive intent of treatment had worse survival than patients treated with prophylactic and adjuvant intent.

Conclusion: Children with cancer have to be treated in highly specialized centers with an experienced team of professionals dedicated to pediatric oncology. Development of referral centres is possible when children are treated by radiation oncologists specialized in pediatric radiotherapy.

Keywords: children, cancer, multimodal treatment, outcome

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